

Studies of tetradentate- N_6 macrocyclic complexes of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

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Abstract : Macrocyclic complexes of copper, nickel and cobalt were synthesized via template reactions. These 1,4,8,11-tetraaza[14]tetraazatetradecatetraene N_6 macrocyclic complexes were characterized by magnetic, conductance, electronic and IR spectral studies. The macrocyclic ligand coordinates through the four azomethine nitrogen atoms which are bridged by 2,3-butanedione moieties, but far infrared spectra suggest the pyridine nitrogens are not coordinated. These macrocyclic complexes are considered to have distorted octahedral configurations.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, tetradentate ligand, template reaction, coordination complexes.

Attention has been paid to the characterization of macrocyclic complexes prepared by the condensation of ketones with transition metal complex of tetraamines. The relationship of electronic properties and reactivities of these synthetic macrocyclic complexes to those of naturally occurring macrocycles, such as porphyrins and corrins, continues to promote great interest in their design and preparation. In this communication, the preparation and properties of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of the 14-membered macrocycles and their derivatives have been reported¹.

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show that the macrocyclic complexes can be represented as $[M(C_{18}H_{18}N_6)X_2]$, where $M = Ni^{II}$, Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- and NCS^- . The conductivity measurements show their non-electrolytic nature and molecular weights of the nickel and cobalt complexes showed that they were monomeric.

Spectral studies :

The spectra of the condensation product of these compounds show various vibrations of pyridine ring and azomethine². By comparing the spectra with those of amine strong band at *ca.* 1625 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at *ca.* 1610 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations, respectively. The absence of bands *ca.* 3300–3200 cm^{-1} indicates that amino groups of 2,6-diaminopyridine have condensed with 2,3-butanedione. This contention is supported by the presence of bands at *ca.* 2925 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 1355 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 1270 cm^{-1} and 680 cm^{-1} characteristic of the 2,3-butanedione moiety and may be assigned to $\nu(CH_3)$, $\nu(C-CH_3)$, $\nu(CH_3)$ and

ring deformation modes. There is no change in pyridine ring vibrations and the nitrogen atom of pyridine does not participate in coordination. Both the amino groups of 2,6-diamino pyridine react with carbonyl groups of 2,3-butanedione forming carbon atom bridge between the two amino groups, similar to those reported in coordinated amines³. The absence of stretching and bending (C-O) group vibrations at *ca.* 1525 cm^{-1} and *ca.* 1280 cm^{-1} also indicate the absence of this group in these macrocyclic complexes. The frequencies of the $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations indicate coordination through this site⁴. Thus in the presence of metal salts, a quadridentate macrocyclic complex is formed which coordinate through azomethine nitrogens while pyridine nitrogen does not take part in coordination. These observations are in accordance with the idea that the formation of quadridentate macrocycles is easier than hexadentate or quidentate macrocycles. It is also evident that azomethine nitrogen, being equally active, excludes coordination through pyridine nitrogen perhaps due to the formation of unstable four membered rings. The far infrared spectra of these complexes show some new bands at *ca.* 310 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 280 cm^{-1} and 275 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $\nu(Co-Cl)$, $\nu(Ni-Cl)$ and $\nu(Cu-Cl)$ vibrations⁴, respectively. Similarly bands in bromo-complexes are observed at *ca.* 225 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 210 cm^{-1} for cobalt and nickel complexes and can be assigned to $\nu(Co-Br)$ and $\nu(Ni-Br)$ vibrational modes. The single bands observed for axial ligation and their regions show that in nitrate complexes the spectra show some new bands at *ca.* 1265 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 1010 cm^{-1} and *ca.* 860 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the monodentate nature of the nitrate group. In thiocyanato complexes, some strong bands appear at *ca.* 2110 cm^{-1} (ν_1), $\nu(C=N)$, *ca.* 480

Table 1. Analytical data of copper, cobalt and nickel macrocyclic complexes

Complex	% of C		N		H		X		M	
	Calcd.	Found								
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Cl ₂	47.73	47.62	18.56	18.40	3.97	3.60	15.69	15.50	14.00	13.90
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Br ₂	39.88	39.50	15.51	15.20	3.32	3.10	29.54	29.40	11.72	11.60
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂	42.72	42.55	16.61	16.20	3.56	3.40	24.53	24.35	12.56	12.50
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NCS) ₂	43.41	43.35	16.88	16.30	3.62	3.35	23.31	23.10	12.76	12.60
Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Cl ₂	48.21	48.00	18.75	18.50	4.01	3.90	15.84	15.65	13.16	13.00
Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Br ₂	40.22	40.10	15.64	15.40	3.35	3.20	29.79	29.65	10.98	10.80
Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂	43.11	43.00	16.76	16.35	3.59	3.40	24.75	24.50	11.77	11.60
Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NCS) ₂	43.81	43.75	17.03	16.80	3.65	3.45	23.52	23.40	11.96	11.80
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Cl ₂	48.25	48.00	18.76	18.20	4.02	3.95	15.86	15.60	13.09	12.90
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)Br ₂	40.25	40.10	15.65	15.40	3.35	3.10	29.81	29.70	10.92	10.80
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂	43.14	43.00	16.77	16.45	3.59	3.45	24.77	24.65	11.70	11.45
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆)(NCS) ₂	43.84	43.50	17.05	16.85	3.65	3.40	23.54	23.45	11.89	11.55

cm⁻¹ (ν_2)NCS bending and *ca.* 830 cm⁻¹ (ν_3), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ of the NCS group, respectively which are in accord with the monodentate N-bonded thiocyanato group. The appearance of new bands at *ca.* 225–245 cm⁻¹ support the coordination of nitrate and thiocyanate groups, which are assignable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ of the nitrate group and *ca.* 260–280 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{NCS})$, respectively. The appearance of bands in the region 430–495 cm⁻¹ shows $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ (azomethine) vibrational modes and confirms the involvement of azomethine nitrogen. The electronic spectra of copper complexes show a maximum at *ca.* 17810–19315 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at *ca.* 14540–17110 cm⁻¹. This indicates that these macrocyclic complexes are distorted octahedral⁴. The shifting of bands towards higher energy is in the order : NCS⁻ > NO₃⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻, i.e. in order of weakening interaction of the metal ion with the anions. Assuming tetragonal distortion in the molecule, the energy level sequence for these complexes may be, $x^2-y^2 > z^2 > xy > xz > yz$ and the shoulder can be assigned to $z^2 \rightarrow x^2-y^2$ (${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$) and the broad band contains both the $xy \rightarrow x^2-y^2$ (${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$) and $xz, yz \rightarrow x^2-y^2$ (${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$) transitions⁵. The separation of bands in the spectra of these complexes is of the order of 2520 cm⁻¹ which is in accordance with the proposed geometry of the complexes⁶. The nickel complexes show three strong bands at *ca.* 10610–12355, 15000–17000 and 25000–28100 cm⁻¹ a shoulder at *ca.* 8500–9510 cm⁻¹ towards low energy side of the first band. The spectral bands are well within the range for hexacoordinate octahedral complexes of nickel reported earlier⁷. The first two bands result from the splitting of one band, n_1 , and can be assigned ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (ν_2) assuming

the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} (components of ${}^3T_{2g}$ in Oh symmetry) and the other two higher bands can be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, 3F_g (ν_3) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(P)$. The intense higher energy band appeared at *ca.* 35060 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the C=N group. A regular pattern is not followed by various bands and this seems to be anion independent. The spectral data are consistent with the distorted octahedral nature of these macrocyclic complexes. The values calculated for Dq^{xy} and Dq^z are given in Table 2. Thus, all the complexes studied herein show pseudo octahedral geometry conforming to D_{4h} symmetry. The values given in the Table 2 indicate that these macrocyclic complexes are moderately distorted and the distortion increases in the order given here : NCS⁻ > NO₃⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. The spectral bands appeared at *ca.* 8255–8750 cm⁻¹ (ν_1) and 15750–16260 cm⁻¹ (ν) with a broad band *ca.* 21050 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) can be assigned to Co^{II} complexes⁸ reported to the distorted octahedral having D_{4h} symmetry. These macrocyclic complexes exhibit the band in the visible region which shows a structure and splitting due to low symmetry field. The splitting cause's band overlap and some broad bands are observed. Thus, assuming the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} , these bands observed can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ at *ca.* 8510, 1620 and 20060 cm⁻¹, respectively. The first band (ν_1) is in the visible region and the assignment of the visible band to ${}^4A_{2g}$ cannot be spin forbidden. The values of Dq , B , β and ν_2/ν_1 ratio are given in Table 2.

The magnetic measurements data of these complexes are given in Table 2. The magnetic moments of cobalt, nickel and copper complexes lie in the ranges 4.81–5.12,

Table 2. Electronic spectral and magnetic data of cobalt and nickel macrocyclic complex

Complex	Spectral data (cm^{-1})	Molecular Weight (Calcd.)	Molecular Weight (Found)	Molar conductance (Ω^{-1})	μ B.M. (300 K)
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)\text{Cl}_2$	21560, 18640, 15895, 8650	448.93	462.93	10.28	4.92
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)\text{Br}_2$	21490, 18470, 16260, 8270	537.73	551.73	9.80	4.90
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)(\text{NO}_3)_2$	21480, 18550, 15770, 8560	501.87	515.93	5.24	5.12
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)(\text{NCS})_2$	21520, 18460, 16140, 8740	494.05	507.93	10.00	4.81
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)\text{Cl}_2$	34840, 27846, 18190, 11720, 10730	447.69	462.69	11.26	3.40
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)\text{Br}_2$	35050, 28210, 18230, 11780, 10740	536.49	551.49	9.75	3.31
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)(\text{NO}_3)_2$	35210, 28330, 18270, 11790, 10640	500.63	515.69	5.20	3.24
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6)(\text{NCS})_2$	34770, 28290, 18240, 11680, 10580	492.81	507.69	9.84	3.35

3.24–3.35 and 1.75–1.86 B.M respectively, at room temperature. The magnetic data are in accordance with the high spin nature of the nickel and cobalt complexes and give the indication of a pseudo octahedral environment around the metal ions. The distorted octahedral environment arises due to the steric interaction of the 2,6-diaminopyridine rings with methyl substituents on the macrocyclic ring. The structure of macrocyclic complexes (A) can be represented in Fig. 1.

1,4,8,11-Tetraaza[14]tetradecatetraene N_6 $M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-, \text{NCS}^-$ **Fig. 1**

Experimental

2,6-Diaminopyridine (0.02 mol) and 2,3-butanedione (0.02 mol) were mixed in a minimum quantity of MeOH and a MeOH solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) was added; the mixture was refluxed for 12 h, HCl added and continued reflux for 2–3 h more. The mixture was concentrated to half and left for 2 days. The greenish brown and reddish coloured crystals were filtered off, washed with methanol, ether dried in vacuum. The complexes so obtained are stable upto 200 °C and are soluble in CH_3OH , DMSO, CH_3CN whereas copper complexes are partially soluble in these solvents. The derivatives of these complexes were prepared by metathesis by stirring and adding slowly NaBr and NH_4CN solutions to an ethanolic solution of metal chloride and NaCl, NH_4NCS , formed during exchange reaction, were filtered off. The nitrate complexes were prepared from metal nitrate salts. The metal contents were determined by spectrophotometric methods while halides were estimated by Volhard's method and nitrate as nitron salt.

Magnetic measurements were carried out using a Princeton Applied Research Model 155 vibrating sample magnetometer incorporating a digital read out. The electromagnet current was maintained using a Polytronic Constant current Regulator Type CP-200. The instrument was calibrated using a standard pure nickel pellet and

cross checked against $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrate. Infra-red spectra in the range of $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer Perkin-Elmer-1800 at room temperature. Electronic spectra covering the $16000\text{--}32000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-VIS double beam spectrophotometer at room temperature using 10 mm glass cells.

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